

Migration Strategies from C-Band to C+L-Band/Multi-Fiber Solutions in Optical Metropolitan Area Networks

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Abstract We investigate practical strategies for migration from C-band to C+L-band/multi-fiber solutions in MAN networks from a Telco operator's perspective through a MAN-customized algorithm supporting multi-homing based on link-and-node-disjoint-path routing. We show $k=3$ shortest paths minimizes the need for new fibers. ©2023 The Author(s)

Introduction

With the increasing demand for data, traditional optical transport networks that are restricted to the C-band spectrum are facing difficulties in keeping up with traffic growth. Telco operators are exploring two approaches to increase available spectral resources: increasing spectral dimensions or spatial dimensions^{[1],[2]}. Both solutions have been extensively studied and have their own pros and cons^[3]. While relying on well-established C-band technology and parallel systems, growing on spatial dimensions is currently limited by the absence of commercial integrated network elements that can manage multiple spatial dimensions simultaneously, and deploying multi-core or few-mode fiber incurs additional costs^[2]. On the other hand, growing on spectral dimensions does not necessitate new fiber deployment/leasing, but requires optimization of launch power and amplifier gain to mitigate the Stimulated Raman Scattering (SRS) effect^[4] and current commercial solutions are limited to the C+L bands (≤ 12 THz). To determine the most cost-effective solution, Telco operators must consider factors such as fiber availability, network topology, and operational issues^[5]. These factors suggest two potential transitional strategies: deploying multi-band/multi-fiber solutions on all links from day one or gradually adding resources through a pay-as-you-grow (PAYG) scheme. In this regard, in^{[5],[6]}, migration from C- to C+L-band was investigated and PAYG was found to be the most cost-effective strategy. These studies, as well as^{[9],[7]-[9]}, focused on backbone networks, but there is a need to further examine the feasibility and performance of these strategies in different network architectures. Telco operators are particularly interested in optical Metro area networks (MAN) due to their higher rate of traffic

growth, driven by the increasing demand for high-bandwidth applications such as video streaming, cloud computing, and the Internet of Things (IoT). Multi-band strategies are particularly well-suited for these networks due to the shorter distances involved, which results in a lower impact on performance caused by SRS. In this paper, we investigate practical mid-term migration strategies to C+L-band/multi-fiber network solutions in densely populated MANs that are compatible with a PAYG approach. To do this, we develop a multi-layer, multi-homed traffic engineering tool that is specifically customized to address the characteristics of MANs. Unlike^{[10],[11]}, where partially link-and-node-disjoint (LAND) primary and secondary paths (PSP) are selected, our tool is designed to find the best routing and spectrum allocation strategy that guarantees LAND PSPs, while minimizing the use of spectral and spatial resources. This study lays the groundwork for a future cost and techno-economic evaluation.

System Model

We examine the topology of Telefonica's MAN depicted in Fig.1.(a), composed of 157 optical nodes and 220 links. The network is divided into hierarchical levels at the IP layer^[10], but this study focuses on the four highest levels (HL1-HL4). The interconnection nodes (HL1) are at the top of the hierarchy and function as interfaces to other telecom providers and the internet, while the transit nodes (HL2) connect the HL3 aggregation nodes to the HL1 nodes and also host significant data centers. Finally, the HL4 nodes aggregate traffic from the access points. This hierarchical distribution separates out the physical topology into three independent network segments, i.e., HL4, HL3, and HL2 as depicted in Fig.1.(a). IP traffic is transmitted from each

Fig. 1: (a)MAN network topology, (b) an illustrative example for traffic aggregation from HL4s to HL1s. P1-P7 are the IP logical primary paths, and S1-S7 are the IP logical secondary paths. P: Primary, S: Secondary,

node to two different nodes belonging to an immediately higher hierarchical level (multi-homing). In order not to impose further restrictions on the multi-period and multi-layer routing, modulation format, spectrum, band, and fiber pair assignment (**RMSBFA**), we assume that all optical nodes are equipped with colorless, directionless, and contentionless re-configurable optical add-drop multiplexers and sufficient bandwidth-variable transponders (BVTs) or fixed capacity transponders operating under a license-based client-port activation scheme, whereby the number of 100G licenses is calculated from $\lceil (R - R_{res})/100 \rceil$, where R_{res} is the residual vacancy from previous years. The chosen throughput, symbol rate, roll-off factor, channel spacing, and pre-FEC BER overhead are 100-400 Gbps, 40 GBaud, 0.1, 50 GHz, and 25%, respectively.

Proposed Planning Tool: RMSBFA

We propose a multi-period and multi-layer planning strategy consisting of seven steps: **1**-Partition the network into three domains (HL4, HL3, and HL2 domains); **2**-Identify all candidate destinations from the HLx nodes in the HLx domain; **3**-Pre-calculate all paths between the HLx nodes in the HLx domain and the selected candidate destinations according to minimum hop number or shortest distance; **4**-Find all LAND PSPs (primary and secondary paths from each HLx node to two destination nodes) in the path list in **step 3**; **5**-Calculate the number of required transponders according to the requested bit-rate (R) from $\lceil R - R_{res}/R_{base} \rceil$, where R_{res} , and $R_{base,m}$ are the residual (i.e. already in use) and base (maximum) capacity of the transponder works with selected modulation format m , and perform the spectrum, band, and fiber-pair assignment based on the first-fit ap-

proach for all k candidate PSPs; **6**-Select the optimum PSP based on the minimum cost of the candidate PSPs, i.e., $C_p = \sum_{l=1}^{M_p} N_{l,p} L_{l,p}$, where C_p , M_p , $N_{l,p}$, and $L_{l,p}$ are the cost function for PSP p , the total number of links that are part of the primary and secondary routes in PSP p , the number of fiber pairs in link l of PSP p , and the length of link l in PSP p ; **7**-Aggregate the traffic from each HLx node at the two destinations to which it is paired. Thus, half of the traffic is homed to each of the destinations. In a multi-homing approach, to ensure survivability, only 50% of the aggregated IP traffic is provisioned to each of the transponders connected to the two upper HL nodes, but, in order to guarantee that all traffic can reach the next hierarchical level in case of a link or node failure, the provisioned capacity of optical channels (OC) from both transponders is calculated according to the equations in Fig.1.(b). Node-failure robustness is ensured by forbidding co-located HL3 nodes to connect to co-located HL2 nodes. Three migration strategies are proposed based on PAYG: (1) C+NFP, (2) C+SupC+NFP, and (3) C+SupC+L+NFP, where NFP stands for "New Fiber Pair". 4.8 THz C-band is used in C+NFP, where new C-band systems are deployed when the requested throughput exceeds the available resources in the existing. For C+SupC+NFP, we consider the same approach but the available spectrum in the NFPs is 6 THz. Moreover, SupC transponders are deployed when the C-band cannot accommodate more traffic in a given link, but in this case, due to the continuity constraint, all links that are part of the end-to-end path need to be migrated to SupC. Once the SupC resources are exhausted, an NFP is used. The same strategy is considered for C+SupC+L+NFP, with a total bandwidth

Fig. 2: Cumulative FP usage in km (blue - related to the left axis) and in a number of links (red - related to the right axis) for $k = 1, 3, 5,$ and $10,$ and for domains (a) HL4, (b) HL3, (c) HL2, and (d) total network, over ten years.

Fig. 3: Blue lines: cumulative FP length in km (top) and number of BVT (bottom). Red lines: number of nodal degrees (top) and 100G licenses (100GL) (bottom). (a)-(b) C+NFP, (c)-(d) C+SupC+NFP, (e)-(f) C+SupC+L+NFP. Results shown over ten years, for all HLs, bands, and total network, with $k = 3.$

of 12.5 THz per fiber pair and a 500-GHz (≈ 4.2 nm) guard band between the C- and the L-band.

Simulations, Results, and Conclusions

For $k = 1,$ and $\leq 3, 5,$ and 10 shortest paths, the performance of the three migration strategies is evaluated with the topology shown in Fig.1.(a). The aggregated traffic at the HL4 nodes is uniformly generated in the range of 20-200 Gbps with an average of 100 Gbps, with a 40% CAGR, according to^[12]. PM-32QAM and PM-64QAM are considered for the lightpaths longer and shorter than 150 km, respectively, based on maximum reach distances obtained from^[13]. We select PM-32QAM 300G and PM-64QAM 400G transponders (based on a 100G licensing scheme) with 50-GHz channel spacing and pre-FEC BER 10^{-3} and consider k shortest path $k = 1,$ and $k \leq 3, 5, 10.$ The number of 50-GHz channels is 96, 120, and 240 for strategies 1-3, respectively.

Fig 2 reveals that NFP length can be reduced by increasing k from 1 to 3, but $k > 3$ adversely affects performance due to the limited number of PSPs in all domains, in particular, HL4 and HL2. Likewise, a higher k results in the establishment of longer lightpaths, thus requiring a greater NFP length. $k=3$ leads to a reduction of 32% and 20% in NFP deployment length, and 53% and 15% in NFP links, compared with $k=1$ and $k=5,$ respectively. The reduction in the number of links is particularly significant as each NFP link requires the installation of a new optical line system (ROADM, inline amplifier). In Fig 3, the cumula-

tive FP length, as well as the number of nodal degrees, BVTs, and 100G licenses are plotted for the three strategies under study. The HL4 domain can serve the traffic demand over the 10-year period without resorting to additional spectral bands or NFPs. This is not the case for the HL3 or HL2 domains, which requires NFPs from year 6/7. However, the C+SupC+L+NFP achieves NFP length savings of 75% and 81% in year 10 compared with C+SupC+NFP and C+NFP, respectively, but also requires, as shown in Fig 3.(f), SuperC- and L-band BVTs, which will impact the Capex and Opex over the second five-year period (8.3% and 20.8% of BVTs are SupC-band and L-band BVTs in year 10). Regarding the nodal degree, we observe an increase of 55%, 39% and 7% for strategies C+NFP, C+SupC+NFP, and C+SupC+L+NFP, respectively, in year 10, which means a reduction in the number of new degrees of 87% comparing C+SupC+L+NFP with C+NFP, even though 22% of the nodes will require L-band WSS for C+SupC+L+NFP. In conclusion, we have shown, by using a customized traffic engineering tool that selects $k = 3$ link and node disjoint shortest paths, that the migration of C+L band in a MAN network belonging to a densely populated area brings significant benefits in terms of reduced fiber deployment/leasing requirements, with the associated savings in new WSS equipment. However, the L-band BVT cost will be an important factor to consider in the techno-economic evaluation of the proposed solution.

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